

DEEPONETS MEETS MCMC: FAST AND SCALABLE BAYESIAN CALIBRATION USING DEEPONETS AS DIFFERENTIABLE SURROGATE MODELS IN HAMILTONIAN MCMC METHODS

João Pedro dos S. Rocha¹ - joaopedro0498@hotmail.com

Márcio Borgers¹ - mrborges@lncc.br

Gilson Giraldi¹ - gilson@lncc.br

José Luiz Faccini² - jose.faccini@colaborador.ien.gov.br

¹Laboratório Nacional de Computação Científica - Petrópolis - RJ

²Instituto de Engenharia Nuclear - Rio de Janeiro - RJ

Abstract. Hamiltonian Monte Carlo (HMC) is a powerful Markov Chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) method that leverages gradient information to accelerate Bayesian inference. However, its adoption in industrial and scientific applications is often limited by the high computational cost of gradient evaluations, particularly when solutions rely on numerical differential equation solvers and in high dimensionality problems. We explore solving this challenge by leveraging Deep Operator Networks (DeepONets) as differentiable surrogate models, enabling efficient gradient computations via automatic differentiation. DeepONets learn nonlinear operators from data, providing fast and accurate approximations of complex system dynamics while preserving gradient information critical for HMC, specially so when using its Physics Informed variations. By replacing the simulator and leveraging automatic differentiation we can achieve significant speedups over traditional methods. This has the potential to unlock real-time Bayesian inference for uncertainty-aware systems. In this work we explore the approach using a 1D simple problem - the Damped Oscillator - going from the traditional approach and incrementally leveraging the DeepONets capabilities up to using HMC. We found that even in such a simple problem on which numerical gradient calculations are feasible the method showed substantial speedups of up to 100x while loosing little precision.

Keywords: DeepONets, Surrogate Modeling, Bayesian Inference, MCMC, HMC

1 INTRODUCTION

Uncertainty quantification (UQ) is a crucial step in parameter estimation pipelines, as it underpins the reliability of scientific and industrial predictions. However, incorporating UQ often introduces a significant computational burden (Volodina and Challenor 2021). Bayesian inference provides a principled framework for addressing this challenge, with several established strategies such as Variational Inference, Nested Sampling, and Markov Chain Monte Carlo (MCMC). Among these, MCMC remains a preferred choice due to its flexibility, scalability, and strong theoretical guarantees. Yet, these advantages come at a high cost: MCMC

requires repeated evaluations of the likelihood function across parameter space, which may itself involve computationally intensive numerical solvers and rejection sampling procedures.

To mitigate these costs, numerous variants of the classical Metropolis algorithm (Metropolis et al. 1953) have been developed, including Metropolis–Hastings (MH) (Hastings 1970), Gibbs sampling (Geman and Geman 1984), and Hamiltonian Monte Carlo (HMC) (Duane et al. 1987). These methods adapt the proposal distribution to improve sampling efficiency while retaining the theoretical robustness of the original formulation. Among them, HMC stands out as particularly powerful, since it leverages gradient information to accelerate convergence and exploration of the posterior. However, its applicability in scientific and industrial contexts is often constrained by the cost of gradient evaluations, especially when these depend on numerical ODE/PDE solvers or arise in high-dimensional problems.

A common strategy to reduce computational overhead is the use of surrogate models, which approximate the original simulator at a fraction of the cost. While traditional surrogate methods, such as polynomial chaos, suffer severely from the curse of dimensionality neural networks have shown more favorable scaling properties. Modern machine learning frameworks such as PyTorch and JAX provide automatic differentiation capabilities, enabling surrogate models to be seamlessly integrated into gradient-based inference methods, including HMC (e.g. Deveney, Mueller, and Shardlow (2023)).

In recent years, physics-informed machine learning (PIML) has emerged as a particularly promising approach for building surrogate models in scientific domains (e.g. Suzuki et al. (2023)). By embedding knowledge of governing dynamics into the learning process, PIML methods improve accuracy and generalization. Examples include physics-informed neural networks (PINNs) (Raissi, Perdikaris, and Karniadakis 2019), Neural Operators (Kovachki et al. 2021), and hybrid approaches augmented with numerical simulators. These methods combine the efficiency of machine learning with the reliability of physics-based modeling.

In this work, we propose addressing the computational bottleneck of HMC by leveraging Deep Operator Networks (DeepONets) (Lu et al. 2021) as differentiable surrogate models. DeepONets are designed to learn nonlinear operators from data, yielding fast and accurate approximations of system dynamics, reducing the computational cost of MCMC, while preserving gradient information crucial for HMC. Implemented within the JAX framework (Bradbury et al. 2018), this approach allows automatic differentiation over the surrogate model and likelihood function composition, enabling efficient gradient-based sampling. In particular physics-informed variants of DeepONets (Wang, Wang, and Perdikaris 2021) has the potential to further enhance accuracy and efficiency. By replacing costly numerical solvers with differentiable DeepONets, we aim to unlock real-time Bayesian inference in complex, uncertainty-aware systems.

Here we illustrate this approach with a simple case study: the one-dimensional damped oscillator. The main contribution of this paper is the following:

- A novel application of DeepONets as differentiable surrogate models for HMC — to the best of our knowledge, this is the first exploration of this combination in the literature.

The remaining text is organized as follows: In section Section 2 we start by describing the general workflow and then the specifics of the demonstration problem. In Section 3 we show the associated results with each experiment, then close with our concluding remarks and work in progress.

2 METHODOLOGY

We setup the demonstration problem in 3 experiments to explore different aspects of the approach. Let's start by describing the general structure after briefly describing our setup.

2.1 Hardware and Programming

All experiments were run in a server equipped with a Ryzen Threadripper PRO 5975WX CPU, and 2 Nvidia RTX A6000 GPUs from the National Laboratory for Scientific Computing, Petrópolis-RJ-Brazil (LNCC). They were all programmed in Python and available on a github repository¹. The environment was captured using the uv package manager² making it readily reproducible (lockfile in the GitHub repo).

2.2 General structure

We consider inverse problems with the following structure: given a dataset \mathcal{D} of measurements $\{y_i\}$ at points $\{x_i\}$, we wish to identify the parameters $\theta \in \mathbb{R}^n$ of a differential equation model. The system is described by:

$$\mathcal{L}_\theta[u](x) = 0 \quad (1.)$$

Where $u(x)$ is the field variable and \mathcal{L}_θ is a differential operator (e.g., $-\nabla \cdot (c\nabla u)$) parameterized by θ . The measurements are modeled as $y_i = u(x_i) + \varepsilon_i$. In Bayesian terms the inverse problem is framed as finding the parameters θ that maximizes the posterior probability $P(\theta | \mathcal{D})$, representing the probability of the parameters given the data. A complete solution also provides confidence intervals for the estimated θ to assess uncertainty, that can be naturally extracted from the posterior distribution, which is defined in Bayes theorem Eq. 2.

$$P(\theta | \mathcal{D}) = \frac{P(\mathcal{D} | \theta)P(\theta)}{P(\mathcal{D})} \quad (2.)$$

The computational pipeline for Bayesian inference using a DeepONet surrogate consists of two main components: the surrogate model and the MCMC sampler Fig. 1. First, training data is generated by executing a high-fidelity numerical solver across a range of parameters θ relevant to the problem domain. This data is partitioned for training and validating the DeepONet. For inference, we create a noisy artificial dataset \mathcal{D} by generating clean data from the solver for a fixed θ^* and corrupting it with additive Gaussian noise. The trained DeepONet surrogate is then integrated into a Bayesian framework. It provides fast evaluations of the model output needed to compute the likelihood function $P(\mathcal{D} | \theta)$. We specify prior distributions $P(\theta)$ and use MCMC sampling (specifically, 10,000 samples per chain) to draw from the posterior $P(\theta | \mathcal{D})$. Finally, we assess MCMC convergence and analyze the posterior distributions using the ArviZ toolbox (Kumar et al. 2019). The difference for the reference solution is that there is no training step and we start directly defining the likelihood in terms of the numerical simulator.

¹<https://github.com/jpssrocha/deeponet-jax-inversion>

²<https://docs.astral.sh/uv/>

Figure 1: General pipeline for DeepONet based workflow

The detailed implementation will be explained in the following sections, starting with the physical model.

2.3 Physical Model and Simulations

As mentioned our demonstration model is the classical damped oscillator problem, which comes from a simple application of Newton's 2nd law (Eq. 3).

$$\frac{d^2x}{dt^2} + \frac{\beta}{m} \frac{dx}{dt} + \frac{k}{m}x = 0 \quad (3.)$$

Subject to:

$$x(t = 0) = x_0 \quad (4.)$$

And:

$$\frac{dx}{dt}(t = 0) = v_0 \quad (5.)$$

To simplify notation we let $m = 1$, then we have a model with one input t and one output x and 4 parameters so $\theta = (\beta, k, x_0, v_0)$.

To solve it numerically we use the `odeint` routine from the SciPy package (Virtanen et al. 2020) which is based on the highly optimized and established FORTRAN library `odepack`.

2.4 Model training

The training data was generated using `odeint` to generate simulations over the cartesian product on the range of $[0, 5]$ in increments of 0.2 for each parameter. Generating almost 400,000 datasets that were then prepared for training the network.

The DeepONet was implemented using the Jax library (Bradbury et al. 2018) and its ecosystem (DeepMind et al. 2020), with the Equinox framework (Kidger and Garcia 2021) for model definition. This choice was motivated by the need for a fully differentiable pipeline to compute the likelihood function.

The network follows the unstacked DeepONet architecture (Lu et al. 2021) Fig. 2, featuring separate branch and trunk networks. Both networks are standard Multi-Layer Perceptrons (MLPs) with identical depth but input dimensions specific to their respective inputs (parameters θ and coordinates x). All hidden layers use ReLU activation functions, while the final layer is linear.

Models were trained using the mean squared error (MSE) loss and the Adam optimizer. Training proceeded for approximately 200,000 epochs, halting once the training loss converged to the order of 10^{-4} .

Figure 2: Stacked DeepONet representation

2.5 Bayesian Inference and Evaluation

To evaluate the full potential of our differentiable surrogate model, we performed Bayesian inference using two complementary Markov Chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) samplers: one gradient-free and one gradient-based. For:

- **Gradient-free Sampling:** We used the Affine-Invariant Ensemble Sampler implemented in the EMCEE package [(Foreman-Mackey et al. 2013); (Goodman and Weare 2010)]. This algorithm efficiently explores the posterior distribution by using an ensemble of walkers that share information to adapt the proposal distribution.
- **Gradient-based Sampling:** We employed the No-U-Turn Sampler (NUTS) (Homan and Gelman 2014), a state-of-the-art Hamiltonian Monte Carlo (HMC) method, via the NumPyro package (Phan, Pradhan, and Jankowiak 2019), which is fully compatible with JAX. This approach leverages the gradients of the posterior—readily available through our JAX-based surrogate—for highly efficient sampling in high-dimensional spaces.

Both samplers were used with their default configurations and using a Gaussian likelihood with fixed variance and uniform a prior over the range on which the DeepONet was trained on.

The resulting chains were analyzed using the ArviZ library (Kumar et al. 2019). We assessed convergence by calculating the \hat{R} statistic as defined in (Vehtari et al. 2021) and monitoring acceptance rates. Finally, we validated the inference by examining the posterior distributions to ensure they were consistent with the true parameter values used to generate the artificial dataset.

With these elements we conducted three experiments to dissect the performance gains:

- **Baseline (Simulator + EMCEE):** Our ground-truth reference.

- Speed (DeepONet + EMCEE): To measure the inference speed improvement.
- Speed & Gradients (DeepONet + NumPyro): To measure the added benefit of gradient-based sampling.

This design separates the impact of the surrogate’s speed from the advantages of its differentiability.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Our results are presented on the following order: we start by presenting a profiling of the probability functions on each scheme, then we show its convergence, and finally if its consistent with the chosen parameters for the artificial dataset.

3.1 Performance Profiling

To quantify the computational benefits of our surrogate model, we profiled the evaluation time of the likelihood functions themselves, isolating them from sampler specific overheads and optimizations. We compared the numerical simulator (odeint) against the trained DeepONet, measuring pure evaluation and gradient calculation time using Python’s standard timing facilities.

For gradient calculations, we compared finite-difference approximations - via the numdifftools package (Perktold 2014) - combined with ODEINT and the DeepONet, as well as gradients computed by JAX’s autograd over the DeepONet. Results, averaged over seven runs, are presented in Table 1.

Model + Gradient Method	Time to Run / <i>ms</i>	Gradient calculation / <i>ms</i>
ODEINT + numdiff	116.00 ± 0.41	154.00 ± 0.29
DEEPONET + numdiff	0.89 ± 0.13	54.90 ± 0.21
DEEPONET + autograd	0.89 ± 0.13	3.67 ± 0.07

Table 1: Timing results

Surprisingly even for a problem with only four parameters, the DeepONet surrogate provided a speedup of two orders of magnitude for likelihood evaluations. The advantage of automatic differentiation over finite-difference methods was similarly significant, showing a speedup of almost 50x.

3.2 Convergence Analysis

The convergence of the Markov chains was evaluated using the split- \hat{R} statistic (Vehtari et al. 2021), with results shown in Fig. 3.

As expected, the ensemble sampler (EMCEE) required a significant number of iterations — approximately 1,000 samples — to converge below the standard threshold of 1.1 and even more to reach the stricter threshold of 1.01. In contrast, the NUTS sampler (NumPyro) exhibited the

desired behavior: following its warm-up phase, the \hat{R} values immediately indicated convergence (i.e., were consistently below the threshold). This demonstrates that the gradients provided by the differentiable DeepONet surrogate are of sufficient quality for the effective operation of the Hamiltonian Monte Carlo algorithm.

Figure 3: Evolution of \hat{R} over iterations

Average acceptance rates were around 55% for EMCEE and around 100% for NumPyro (as expected from a Hamiltonian sampler). This reveals an even more pronounced speed gain, because of HMC, since less proposals are necessary to reach the desired number of samples and with less samples to reach convergence.

3.3 Posteriors

The true parameters used to generate the artificial dataset was $(\beta, k, x_0, v_0) = (0.3, 1.5, 1.1, 1.2)$. We present the mean, standard deviation and the 95% confidence interval for each parameter starting with β in Table 2.

Setup	Mean	Standard Deviation	95%CI
ODEINT + EMCEE	0.315	0.241	0.186-0.406
DEEPONET + EMCEE	0.303	0.175	0.201-0.415
DEEPONET + NumPyro	0.293	0.057	0.199-0.410

Table 2: Posterior Statistics - β

Setup	Mean	Standard Deviation	95%CI
ODEINT + EMCEE	1.485	0.220	1.317-1.626
DEEPONET + EMCEE	1.480	0.119	1.321-1.628
DEEPONET + NumPyro	1.475	0.078	1.323-1.628

Table 3: Posterior Statistics - k

Setup	Mean	Standard Deviation	95%CI
ODEINT + EMCEE	1.179	0.163	0.885-1.466
DEEPONET + EMCEE	1.150	0.168	0.838-1.459
DEEPONET + NumPyro	1.154	0.157	0.850-1.461

Table 4: Posterior Statistics - x_0

Setup	Mean	Standard Deviation	95%CI
ODEINT + EMCEE	1.216	0.311	0.683-1.722
DEEPONET + EMCEE	1.252	0.270	0.732-1.773
DEEPONET + NumPyro	1.249	0.265	0.753-1.787

Table 5: Posterior Statistics - v_0

The posterior statistics for all experimental setups are largely consistent, successfully recovering the true parameter values used to generate the dataset. This indicates that the DeepONet surrogate provides a statistically valid approximation of the forward model.

Crucially, all methods produce coherent results, validating that the proposed framework can not only achieves substantial computational speedups but also retain most of the statistical properties of traditional simulation-based inference.

4 FINAL REMARKS AND FUTURE WORK

This work successfully demonstrated a framework for accelerating Bayesian inverse problems by integrating DeepONet surrogates with modern MCMC samplers. The trained DeepONet provided a computationally efficient and fully differentiable approximation of the numerical solver’s response, achieving speedups of up to two orders of magnitude for likelihood evaluations.

Our experiments confirmed that the surrogate produces statistically coherent results, accurately recovering true parameters with posterior distributions consistent with the traditional simulator-based approach. Furthermore, we showed that leveraging the surrogate’s gradients through Hamiltonian Monte Carlo (NumPyro) not only maintains accuracy but also yields superior sampling efficiency compared to gradient-free methods (EMCEE).

In summary, the proposed methodology offers a powerful and rigorous alternative for parameter inference in differential equation models, combining the significant speed of surrogate modeling with the statistical guarantees of full Bayesian inference.

As of writing this manuscript, the efficacy of this framework was further supported by promising preliminary results from a more complex case with 24 parameters in a well engineering case. Future work will focus on refining this result, testing more complex governing equations and physics integration for better gradients through Physics-Informed DeepONets.

Acknowledgements

This study was financed in part by the Coordenação de Aperfeiçoamento de Pessoal de Nível Superior (CAPES) – Brasil. We also thank the Laboratório Nacional de Computação Científica (LNCC) for providing the infrastructure and computational resources that supported this research.

REFERENCES

- Bradbury, James, Roy Frostig, Peter Hawkins, Matthew James Johnson, Chris Leary, Dougal Maclaurin, George Necula, et al. 2018. “JAX: Composable Transformations of Python+NumPy Programs”. 2018. <http://github.com/jax-ml/jax>.
- DeepMind, Igor Babuschkin, Kate Baumli, Alison Bell, Surya Bhupatiraju, Jake Bruce, Peter Buchlovsky, et al. 2020. “The DeepMind JAX Ecosystem”. 2020. <http://github.com/google-deepmind>.
- Deveney, Teo, Eike H. Mueller, and Tony Shardlow. 2023. “Deep Surrogate Accelerated Delayed-Acceptance Hamiltonian Monte Carlo for Bayesian Inference of Spatio-Temporal Heat Fluxes in Rotating Disc Systems”. *SIAM/ASA Journal on Uncertainty Quantification* 11 (3): 970–95. <https://doi.org/10.1137/22M1513113>.
- Duane, Simon, A.D. Kennedy, Brian J. Pendleton, and Duncan Roweth. 1987. “Hybrid Monte Carlo”. *Physics Letters B* 195 (2): 216–22. [https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/0370-2693\(87\)91197-X](https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/0370-2693(87)91197-X).
- Foreman-Mackey, Daniel, David W. Hogg, Dustin Lang, and Jonathan Goodman. 2013. “emcee: The MCMC Hammer”. *pas* 125 (925): 306. <https://doi.org/10.1086/670067>.
- Geman, Stuart, and Donald Geman. 1984. “Stochastic Relaxation, Gibbs Distributions, And the Bayesian Restoration of Images”. *IEEE Transactions on Pattern Analysis and Machine Intelligence*, no. 6 , 721–41. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TPAMI.1984.4767596>.
- Goodman, Jonathan, and Jonathan Weare. 2010. “Ensemble Samplers with Affine Invariance”. *Communications in Applied Mathematics and Computational Science* 5 (1): 65–80. <https://doi.org/10.2140/camcos.2010.5.65>.
- Hastings, W. K. 1970. “Monte Carlo Sampling Methods Using Markov Chains and Their Applications”. *Biometrika* 57 (1): 97–109. <https://doi.org/10.1093/biomet/57.1.97>.
- Homan, Matthew D., and Andrew Gelman. 2014. “The No-U-Turn Sampler: Adaptively Setting Path Lengths in Hamiltonian Monte Carlo”. *J. Mach. Learn. Res.* 15 (1): 1593–623.

- Kidger, Patrick, and Cristian Garcia. 2021. “Equinox: Neural Networks in JAX via Callable PyTrees and Filtered Transformations”. *Differentiable Programming Workshop at Neural Information Processing Systems 2021*.
- Kovachki, Nikola B., Zongyi Li, Burigede Liu, Kamyar Azizzadenesheli, Kaushik Bhattacharya, Andrew M. Stuart, and Anima Anandkumar. 2021. “Neural Operator: Learning Maps between Function Spaces”. *Corr.* <https://arxiv.org/abs/2108.08481>.
- Kumar, Ravin, Colin Carroll, Ari Hartikainen, and Osvaldo Martin. 2019. “ArviZ a Unified Library for Exploratory Analysis of Bayesian Models in Python”. *Journal of Open Source Software* 4 (33): 1143. <https://doi.org/10.21105/joss.01143>.
- Lu, Lu, Pengzhan Jin, Guofei Pang, Zhongqiang Zhang, and George Em Karniadakis. 2021. “Learning Nonlinear Operators via Deeponet Based on the Universal Approximation Theorem of Operators”. *Nature Machine Intelligence* 3 (3): 218–29. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s42256-021-00302-5>.
- Metropolis, Nicholas, Arianna W. Rosenbluth, Marshall N. Rosenbluth, Augusta H. Teller, and Edward Teller. 1953. “Equation of State Calculations by Fast Computing Machines”. *The Journal of Chemical Physics* 21 (6): 1087–92. <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.1699114>.
- Perktold, Josef. 2014. “Numdiff Package.”
- Phan, Du, Neeraj Pradhan, and Martin Jankowiak. 2019. “Composable Effects for Flexible and Accelerated Probabilistic Programming in NumPyro”. *Arxiv Preprint Arxiv:1912.11554*.
- Raissi, M., P. Perdikaris, and G.E. Karniadakis. 2019. “Physics-Informed Neural Networks: A Deep Learning Framework for Solving Forward and Inverse Problems Involving Nonlinear Partial Differential Equations”. *Journal of Computational Physics* 378:686–707. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcp.2018.10.045>.
- Suzuki, Tomoyuki, Kenji Hirohata, Yasutaka Ito, Takehiro Hato, and Akira Kano. 2023. “Physics-Informed Machine Learning for Surrogate Modeling of Heat Transfer Phenomena”. *Journal of Computational and Nonlinear Dynamics* 18 (11): 111001. <https://doi.org/10.1115/1.4063224>.
- Vehtari, Aki, Andrew Gelman, Daniel Simpson, Bob Carpenter, and Paul-Christian Bürkner. 2021. “Rank-Normalization, Folding, And Localization: An Improved R[^] for Assessing Convergence of MCMC (With Discussion)”. *Bayesian Analysis* 16 (2). <https://doi.org/10.1214/20-ba1221>.
- Virtanen, Pauli, Ralf Gommers, Travis E. Oliphant, Matt Haberland, Tyler Reddy, David Cournapeau, Evgeni Burovski, et al. 2020. “SciPy 1.0: Fundamental Algorithms for Scientific Computing in Python”. *Nature Methods* 17:261–72. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41592-019-0686-2>.
- Volodina, Victoria, and Peter Challenor. 2021. “The Importance of Uncertainty Quantification in Model Reproducibility”. *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society A: Mathematical, Physical and Engineering Sciences* 379 (2197). <https://doi.org/10.1098/rsta.2020.0071>.
- Wang, Sifan, Hanwen Wang, and Paris Perdikaris. 2021. “Learning the Solution Operator of Parametric Partial Differential Equations with Physics-Informed Deeponets”. *Corr.* <https://arxiv.org/abs/2103.10974>.